

Elaborating Environmental Communication within “Posthuman” Theory

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1. Introduction

The need to encourage affirming and sustainable ways of life, and also the courage to dare to critique destructive ways of life, is more than a vision; it is a pedagogical challenge which raises ideas of importance for environmental communication. We follow Richard A. Rogers’ argument that there is a need to take environmental theory seriously and articulate the implications of how these theoretical ideas can be put into practice when it comes to social formation and the natural world, not to mention the affiliations that need to be established to make these practices viable. Sometimes there is an urgent need not only to challenge normalized and allegedly taken-for-granted ideas, but more importantly to actively and radically problematize the anthropocentric teleology of theoretical stances that constitute the notion of ‘understanding’ in relation to environmental awareness in various ways. This text argues for a post-anthropocentric turn that can provide the space for elaborating ideas that can function as the foundation for a critical, posthumanist environmental communication theory.

Environmental communication as an academic field is relatively new, and research in this area has sprung out of activist engagement with ideas of justice, loss of biodiversity, environmental management, democracy, and various environmental crises, among other concerns, and how these issues intersect (see Cox; Peterson, Peterson, and Peterson; Monani). The field of environmental communication focuses on the actions connecting activists and academics to help them strive for “a just and healthy Earth” (Peterson, Peterson, and Peterson 83). This makes environmental communication a meta-field that cuts across disciplines, and ties research and theory together by providing a topical focus on communication and on human relations with and within the environment (Milstein, “Environmental Communication” 344). ‘Environmental education’ and ‘Education for sustainable development’ are examples of activities that develop learning and knowledge formulation within environmental communication as an academic field (see Jurin, Roush, and Danter; Kahn; Sriskandarajah and Wals; Wals).

Environmental communication thus contributes to an increased understanding of environmental matters by focusing on human relations with the environment. This, in turn, generates knowledge in, from, and about the world (Jurin, Roush, and Danter, 15). However, despite the ambition to learn with and from the nonhuman world, environmental communication often devolves into human-centered traditions that

advance the political agenda of changing human behavior. Thus the political agenda of environmental communication includes pedagogical objectives that aim to support a better understanding of the interaction between the human and the nonhuman world. Such an approach can be assumed to originate in a positivist worldview that separates the human cultural and social world from the natural world — a tendency constructivist theory¹ shares, since constructivists actually separate the natural world from the scientifically constructed world through the notion that scientists look at the natural world and construct an idea of it (Braidotti, *Posthuman*; Peterson, Peterson, and Peterson). An issue underlying this concern is explicitly articulated in Peterson, Peterson, and Peterson: “Constructivist epistemologies not only endanger conservation by denying nonhumans citizenship, they cripple conservation initiatives by suggesting that truth is what the powerful believe” (76).

An alternative to the constructivist approach, in which nature and culture are separated, is formulated by Rosi Braidotti, who, following Deleuze among others, claims that nature and culture emerge in a continuum that evolves through variations or differentiations. Braidotti thus counters the constructivist idea of a more or less clear-cut separation between nature and culture (Braidotti, *Transpositions* 205).

Within environmental communication theory, this critique of both positivism and constructivism forms the basis for an alternative radical communication theory. In 1998, Rogers presented ideas stemming from such critiques in his essay “Overcoming the Objectification of Nature in Constitutive Theories: Toward a Transhuman, Materialist Theory of Communication.” Rogers argues for the necessary human immersion in the natural world, and for allowing the inclusion of non-essentialized nonhuman voices in discourse (244). In this radical assertion of communication theory, by arguing for the possibility of working with the notion of power (of which more later) through discursive and natural forces, the importance of avoiding determinism becomes central. To enable a deconstruction of the ideal/material distinction, Rogers highlights the following criteria:

- (1) the resurrection of a place for natural forces, traits, and structures in communication theory while avoiding a return to natural determinism;
- (2) an affirmation that we humans are embodied creatures embedded in a world that is not entirely our own making;
- (3) a rehearsal of ways of listening to nondominant voices and nonhuman agents and their inclusion in the production of meaning, policy, and material conditions;
- (4) the deconstruction of common sense binaries such as subject/object, social/natural, and ideational/material, and a reconstruction of relationships as dialogic: recursive, interdependent, and fluid. Such a theoretical project could enrich the scope of communication theory and criticism while embracing the value and dynamism of the extrasocial world. Old tools tend to reproduce old structures. The reconstruction of a different relationship to the environment in which we live requires radically alternative conceptions of humans, nature, material condition and discourse. (268)

This perspective brings us to Braidotti. The idea of a posthuman nomadic subject as presented in her writing becomes useful when reflecting on how to bring Rogers' criteria into practice. The idea of the nomadic refers to the differentiation and repetition that is understood as territorializing (Deleuze and Guattari 355). The nomadic explains physical as well as psychological changes such as those occurring through learning, joy, depression, love, aging, fears, broken bones, et cetera, together with constitutional materialities such as tools (both mechanical and digital), medicine, artificial hair colors, implants, et cetera, that 'constitute' posthuman nomadic subjects (singularities) (Bennett). Simultaneously the nomadic explains changes that occur through becoming, as the multiple merges with "the one" as (possible) alterations of emerging posthuman nomadic subjects, such as in reproduction or bodily decay when the dew transforms leaves or a human body returns to soil (Bennett; Haraway, *When Species Meet*). Further, the nomadic posthuman subject is political (Braidotti, *Posthuman*). In sum, the nomadic posthuman subject will never *be*; it is in a continuous process of *becoming* (Braidotti, *Posthuman* 188). The concept of the posthuman nomadic subject, we suggest, can provide the basis for profound arguments in support of a post-anthropocentric notion of environmental communication. As Braidotti states:

The posthuman subject is not postmodern, because it does not rely on any anti-foundationalist premises. Nor is it post-structuralist, because it does not function within the linguistic turn or other forms of deconstruction. Not being framed by the ineluctable powers of signification, it is consequently not condemned to seek adequate representation of its existence within a system that is constitutionally incapable of granting due recognition. The posthuman nomadic subject is materialist and vitalist, embodied and embedded — it is firmly located somewhere, according to the radical immanence of the 'politics of location'... It is a multifaceted and relational subject, conceptualized within a monistic ontology, through the lenses of Spinoza, Deleuze and Guattari, plus feminist and post-colonial theories. It is a subject actualized by the relational vitality and elemental complexity that mark posthuman thought itself. (*Posthuman* 188)

This quote, which articulates a path of knowledge whereby material as well as political matters become significant, is key to a posthumanism that will enrich the idea of existence. A posthuman nomadic subject opens up possibilities to acknowledge actions while at the same time not compromising the necessity of thinking and writing critically. This process of becoming posthuman has, as Braidotti intimates, the potential to change the very idea of thinking:

Becoming-posthuman ... is a process of redefining one's sense of attachment and connection to a shared world, a territorial space: urban, social, psychic, ecological, planetary as it may be. It expresses multiple ecologies of belonging, while it enacts the transformation of one's sensorial and perceptual co-ordinates, in order to acknowledge the

collective nature and outward-bound direction of what we still call the self. (*Posthuman* 193)

What Braidotti wants to characterize here is a nomadic posthuman subject that becomes in multiplicity (*Posthuman*). The main point here is that the notion of processuality, i.e., of an attention to and study of processes, becomes of prime importance for a posthuman turn in environmental communication theory. We argue that this turn can empower post-anthropocentric, multiple nomadic expressions for a situation or event. Furthermore, we argue that posthuman/post-anthropocentric environmental communication theory has the potential to change how the knowledge of emerging earthly matters can be understood. Communication theory and practice, especially in environmental communication, need to consider more than anthropocentric history. A post-anthropocentric approach in environmental communication thus includes more than the human perspective, and so provides the possibility of warranting nonhuman citizenship² in environmental milieux (Peterson, Peterson, and Peterson 76).

Communicative processes express a ‘machinic assemblage’,³ that is, communicative procedures of repetition and differentiation which express organizations in various ways. As Spoelstra explains: “‘We’ are equally part of ‘organizations’ as ‘organizations’ are part of ‘us’. ‘We’, as well as ‘organizations’, produce what it means to be a ‘we’ or ‘an organization’ in taking part of the primary processes of formation and deformation — in short: in organizing” (84). ‘Organizations’, moreover, offer up a multitude of expressions for communicational processes (Massumi). This means that in a certain space/time situation, the differentiation⁴ and repetition⁵ of movement and forces will affect the communicative flows in various directions and express various communicative practices.⁶

To develop these thoughts, we will in the following parts of this essay problematize the two concepts that constitute ‘environmental communication’ — that is, environment and communication — for the purpose of challenging anthropocentrism. By elaborating on environmental communication within posthuman theory, we want to enable a radical approach to critically studying situations that express the notion of ‘sustainable development’ as a matter for environmental communication research. ‘Environment’ as a spatial concept and ‘communication’ as a temporal concept for interactions and exchange require location, or perhaps allocation, through a posthuman turn in environmental communication theory.

2. Communication

We argue that communication is a function of and site for relational actions; in other words, communicative actions create the space and time for meaning to emerge through relations. Etymologically, the Latin noun *communicatio* and the verb *communicare* imply that the concept of communication involves the action of sharing (Harper, *Communication*; Peters 6-7). This notion of sharing situates communication in a liminal space of actions and simultaneous becomings in actions as the act of communicating itself. Taken in this sense, communication is about relations and cannot be determined as

an essence (Hayles 91). The major theories within communication research deal with conversation and have mainly focused on linguistic or rhetorical concepts to explain meaning-making in actions (Littlejohn and Foss). Communication as a concept implies a community, which means that a communion of actions can be seen as relational (Jenlink and Banathy xi). This, moreover, implies that an action-space of some kind develops through communication, which, in turn, lets forces and affects emerge that empower the awareness of communicative actions. This implication follows Peters' argument that communication is never an exclusively human transaction, but rather a border-crossing action: "Communication is perhaps the ultimate border crossing concept, traversing the bounds of species, machines, even divinity" (Peters 228). This challenges notions of communication as requiring communicative procedures with a presupposed interacting subject that is often presumed to be human (Peters 227).

Variations within communication theory and communicative actions can be seen in the use of concepts such as dialogue, discussion, and conversation. Discussion is a communicative concept with a pedagogical intent that presupposes the truth and accuracy of specific ideas in the meaning of a problem or a situation negotiated through different perspectives or subject positions (Hayles 73-74). Discussion defined in this way is thus never about learning, but about interpreting a certain negotiated meaning. Discussion implies the "arrangement" of action-spaces through various arguments that are taken to reflect what is true (Hayles 73-75). Moreover, discussion might presuppose the idea of dialogue, but dialogue is always, as Peters writes, "the dream of identical minds in concert" (241). Communicative dialogue demands a shared problem and often has the purpose of reaching a decision and so degrading one idea in relation to another (Dryzek). The dialogical design thus also disqualifies the concept of equality between the subject positions that contribute to the dialogue (Jenlink and Banathy). Dialogue, Catherine Ryther argues, involves a pedagogical orientation toward learning that presupposes a desire for unity (2-3). This type of desire suggests that truth will always be the truth of those who possess power. Conversations, on the other hand, Ryther argues,

emerge in an orientation towards interruption, an interruption which ... disrupts the stable order of the symbolic and opens up the possibility for symbolic freedom.... Learning ... is not about learning a kind of content but about attending to the disruption that irreducible strangeness introduces. (3)

This means that conversation, as a concept, implies actions that enable learning, and thus becomes a way to provide possibilities for learning within communicative actions. Taking conversations as a mode of communication means that the concept of conversation becomes a first step in challenging communication theories grounded in anthropocentrism. Conversation, viewed in this way, involves the movements or interplay of actions of talking and listening, and this allows a becoming of materiality in conversation (Deleuze and Parnet 3). Deleuze and Guattari problematize communication as a concept by analyzing both its content and its expressive sides. In relation to analysis, Deleuze and Guattari hold that "forms of expression and forms of content communicate through a conjunction of their quanta of relative deterritorialization, each intervening,

operating in the other” (Deleuze and Guattari 97). Deleuze and Guattari here clarify their notion of communication as an event that can be explained as relating to two axes; one axis is the ‘machinic assemblage’ of bodies, which includes actions, passions, and intermingling bodies in reaction; the other axis is the ‘collective assemblage of enunciation’, that is, the acts of making statements and the incorporeal transformations that are attributed to bodies (Deleuze and Guattari 97-98). These axes are territorialized in a situation or an event, and stabilize the idea of becoming a machinic assemblage. Simultaneously, the assemblage also deterritorializes, destabilizes, and differentiates the becoming assemblages (Deleuze and Guattari 98). Consequently, communication, in its process, denotes, at the same time, both its content and its expression.

To support these ideas regarding what could be called ‘material movements’ as communicative events, we would like to develop the idea of communication and the function of language within environmental communication, since environmental communication considers material actions and their abstractions as being intertwined with each other as well as mutually dependent on one another. For example, abstractions that are articulated rhetorically through various concepts inevitably become political, or as Claire Colebrook puts it, “Before an actualized language or law there is an affective response, a web of relations or an ecology from which something like the system of lived politics emerges” (Colebrook, “Calculus” 135). Seen in this way, language and law are concepts that develop from forces that affect bodies in transformation to repress the original system of lived politics. Bodies are both embedded in and embodied as an environment, and are thus forced into a politics and a culture that are governed by an anthropocentric discourse.

3. Environment

The concept of environment relates etymologically to a “‘state of being environed’...; ‘the aggregate of the conditions in which a person or thing lives’” (Harper, *Environment*). The etymology implicates that ‘environment’ is a subject-centered concept, since it always refers to a specific subject and its surroundings, its milieu. In striving for a just and healthy Earth, some critical questions continuously have to be asked: “Whose surroundings?” or “Why is one subject, necessarily, the principal one?” Anthropocentrism marks humans as the dominant subjects and situates humanity at the top of the bio-social hierarchy. ‘Environment’ as a subject-centered concept needs to be problematized and challenged, since anthropocentric hierarchies force us to believe that the environment consists solely of the surroundings of human beings, and so Earth becomes a property possessed by humans alone.

We will address this problem by paying attention to why a turn from subject-centrism is important to how we can come to understand environment as a concept. ‘Centrism’ is an idea that can be connected to the archaic belief that the earth was the center of the universe. This geo-centrism expresses the belief that all planets and stars, including the sun, were orbiting the earth. Geo-centrism was, as is well known, challenged by several scientists, for example Nicholas Copernicus, Galileo Galilei, and Johannes Kepler, whose discoveries turned Earth into just one planet among other planets orbiting the sun,

defining this relationship as heliocentric. Heliocentrism refers to the star ‘sun’ and the planets that orbit around it. This idea does not include other stars or galaxies of the universe. The earth, consequently, was decentered in this scientific turn, meaning that the place of observation (the earth) is no longer the center for what is observed, but the center for observations.⁷ A decentered understanding of the point of observation is one of the main arguments for a change from subject-centeredness to a post-anthropocentric perspective on and understanding of the world. This turn allows a radical change in our understanding of the environment as a system of relational actions.

This is what Braidotti implies when she says, “A post-anthropocentric approach allows for a non-binary way of positing the relationship between same and other, between life and death” (“Locating” 99). This approach, furthermore, does not entail ignoring humans or the human body, but provides a way to challenge anthropocentrism. Post-anthropocentrism constitutes a path to challenging the human subject-centeredness in anthropocentrism by turning the idea of being(s), seen as static and determined ‘product(s)’ or ‘thing(s)’, into the idea of becoming, that is, into the processuality of becoming, a processuality of continually becoming as change. In Erin Manning’s writing, this processuality is defined as a conjunction of forces and affects: “The becoming-body takes form only retrospectively in the biogrammatic conjunction of the series. What conjugates the series is the fact that a body will emerge” (Manning 125). In order to begin to think through and conceptualize the concept of ‘environment’, it is important to first recognize and acknowledge that a becoming environmental body is both human and nonhuman. The emergence of bodies is a political becoming, which is something that Colebrook analyzes in an attempt to define and clarify political forces:

The body is neither a brute and determining pre-political given, nor is it an effect of political or ideological representation. Rather, as an idea the body would be the political itself; the body is a relation to what is not itself, a movement or activity from a point of difference to other points of difference. And so difference is neither an imposed scheme on an otherwise uniform substance, nor is difference the relation between already differentiated self-identical entities. What something is, is given through its activity of differentiation. (“From Radical Representations” 87)

To develop the notion of ‘the singular body’ as well as what we call ‘relational affects’,⁸ the concept ‘relationscapes’, developed in Erin Manning’s thinking, is useful. ‘Relationscapes’ refers to a non-subject-oriented approach to understanding environment, a milieu, as a multidimensional spatiality, and its temporal situation as an event. By following forces and affects through actions, that is, by recognizing them as biograms, it is possible to recognize and acknowledge the relationality of becoming assemblages, and the emerging human and nonhuman bodies in relation. Relationscapes as a concept provides a possibility for understanding events as flows and movements that express actions of becoming (Kennedy). To recognize forces that affect emerging bodies means to acknowledge relationscapes as relational, that is, as expressing machinic assemblage.

‘Environment’ as a concept thus turns into the concept of ‘relationscapes’ in the shift from a product-centered representative perspective to the notion of processuality within various expressions. The concept ‘relationscapes’ expresses becoming as a machinic assemblage, giving rise to new perspectives on life (and death), and also explaining the flows and movements of forces and affects within an emerging non-subject-centered environment (Deleuze and Guattari; Deleuze, *Pure Immanence*; Braidotti, “Locating”; Kennedy).

4. Affects: A Pedagogical Turn from Anthropocentrism to Post-Anthropocentrism

Deleuze notes that each situation is an event, and that an event is an expression (*Foucault* 87), and based on Deleuze’s argument, we suggest that coming to understand an event through its movement provides the expression of actions from which meanings emerge. Active knowing involves a situation from which learning emerges, and through which understanding is communicated. This, we suggest, constitutes a pedagogical turn in environmental communication that relates to situations that can be understood post-anthropocentrically.

In Donna Haraway’s writing, the human body becomes a matter for post-anthropocentric or even non-anthropocentric relations in repetition that, precisely, challenges the embodiment of the human biological body as anthropocentric:

[H]uman genomes can be found in only 10 percent of all the cells that occupy the mundane space I call my body; the other 90 percent of the cells are filled with the genomes of bacteria, fungi, protists, and such, some of which play in a symphony necessary to my being alive at all, and some of which are hitching a ride and doing the rest of me, of us, no harm. (*When Species Meet* 3-4)

What Haraway expresses here is how the human body is articulated as an assemblage within what we call relational communication, or communication which shapes biological practice as the assemblage of the human body. This assemblage consists of a set of relationscapes that emerges through relational communication between genes and genomes in a flow of movements. The relationscapes, with inherent forces, affect the biological creature that is defined by the concept “human”; the human being is thus nothing other than materialization in action. Moreover, we argue that biological actions are always social actions that are relational and in relation. This relationality in process gives rise to the fusion of matter and meaning: “Matter and meaning are not separate elements. They are inextricably fused together, and no event, no matter how energetic, can tear them asunder” (Barad, *Meeting* 3). Matter and meaning are the expression and the content that meet in the becoming actions of and for emerging bodies. This can be conceptualized as relationscapes, with flows of forces that affect the various processes for understanding materialities as situations where meaning emerges. What the meaning of a human body can be, taking into account the forces and affects of the conceptual and material matters in communication, is what Deleuze asks about in the form of the following question:

[T]he question is not that of the human compound, whether conceptual or real, perceptible or articulable. The question concerns the forces that make up man: with what other forces do they combine, and what is the compound that emerges? (*Foucault 73*)

To begin to address this question, we assume that the body is a political body, and we furthermore argue that the political is made up of forces within pedagogical actions that affect the emerging relationscapes. One example of these political forces is the androcentric idea that the male human separates from the female human in a hierarchical machinery. From a critical feminist perspective, we get the possibility of recognizing and acknowledging various relationscapes. To understand the potentials of a feminist critique, and to counter the problem inherent in any hierarchy, Colebrook suggests that ‘man’ and ‘woman’ should be seen as part of ‘human’ differentiations in which the significant action is to become woman and not man:

If the idea of “man” is that being who can give birth to himself, create himself anew and be in command of his own futurity, then the idea of “woman” is perhaps that of a being who recognizes that the self is not owner of itself, created through a past that can never be rendered fully self-present. (“Stratigraphic” 12)

By developing this argument, it is possible to propose a non-androcentric approach to the idea of relationscapes. A non-androcentric approach has the potential to express the political forces of feminist actions, since these feminist forces will enact the processuality of becoming, which should not be confused with the existence of a determined being. Colebrook develops a striated⁹ notion of time-space situations regarding man and woman, and also provides a new explanation for the idea of situated knowledge, a concept that Sandra Harding and Donna Haraway (“Situated”) had previously explored. However, we follow Braidotti’s argument concerning this concept, which makes the striated notion of space/time situations useful within environmental theory, in that a nomadic subject becomes political through forces that affect the formation of meaning:

The feminist practice of the politics of locations, later to become situated knowledge, provides the missing link between the theory and the practice of a non-unitary, relational and outward-bound definition of the subject. (*Transpositions 250*)

These actions, we argue, which take place in time/space situations, are the becoming of the political, and are, furthermore, inherently communicative. Thus, becoming, as communication, is a way of thinking that is always in process, through which knowledge becomes the abstraction of communication. Communication, seen as a concept in process, is always performative, and the abstraction of communication is the passage from expression into content. As Massumi notes:

The performative is a direct avenue for the passage of expression into content. Deleuze and Guattari argue that every use of language carries a certain performative force, if only because it presupposes a conventional context of intelligibility, and that conventional girding brings pressure to bear toward a certain manner of response. (19)

In other words, Massumi's notion of the 'lines of flight'¹⁰ of performance (derived from Deleuze and Guattari) coincides with the idea of knowledge as the abstraction within communication. To pursue this idea opens up possibilities for writing performative maps within a liminal temporal and spatial realm of relationality, by writing lines of flight related to various actions. This action generates a situation where learning actions arrange understanding into meaning. Meanings differ within the actual articulation of understanding, and are significant for the differentiated nomadic subjects within the communicative acts. Knowledge is thus the abstraction within communication, and in consequence understanding, or what is known, becomes the content of both matter and meaning in communicative actions. This also relates to memory and to the remembering of various situations as relationscapes. The relationscapes have the possibility of articulating memories to relational members within the relationscapes. These memories are relational and remembered through various performative archives that take on materiality, which provides the possibility of understanding various situations and events.

5. Environmental Communication within Posthuman Theory

Barad's thinking in "Posthuman Performativity" and *Meeting the Universe Halfway* gives us some keys for enabling a "posthuman" environmental communication theory. She questions the place of language in communication theory and highlights the significance of interaction. She challenges the strong emphasis on language in communication theory by focusing on the materiality of language (*Meeting* 132; 211). However, Barad centers on the communicative act, which differs from the notion of becoming that we want to develop in this essay. The focus on making or acting in Barad's thinking turns communication into an apparatus for engagement through intra-actions. In order to understand communicative actions, Barad problematizes interaction as a key concept within communication theory, because interaction as a concept articulates a priori statements of communicators (Barad, *Meeting*; see also Parisi). To challenge the concept 'interaction' through the concept 'intra-action' enables us to understand becoming as processuality within communication theory. As Barad notes, "'intra-action' signifies *the mutual constitution of relata*¹¹ within phenomena (in contrast to 'interaction', which assumes the prior existence of distinct entities)" (*Meeting* 429; emphasis in original).

Interaction emphasizes the process as product, and by exchanging this concept with intra-action, processuality is emphasized. Interaction as a concept is problematic because it presupposes entities a priori, that is, beings that might be confused with being, i.e., beings that are static and determined. Intra-action, Barad argues, is also useful since it contests the traditional fixation on words and things as representational instead of as expressing the relationality between materialities (*Meeting* 139).¹² The discrepancy between Barad's notion of intra-action and the way this concept is used in this text is significant, since

communication, seen as part of the process of becoming, and not only as an activity, relates to both content and actions. The concept of intra-action thus ties in to the idea of ‘becoming material’ (Barad, *Meeting*). This, in turn, challenges the hierarchy within communication theory that poses words as representations (Barad, *Meeting* 139). There are two diverging ideas in this reasoning (using Deleuze and Guattari’s concepts): 1) that of becoming communication as the *collective assemblage of enunciation*, and 2) that of becoming through and within communicative actions as the *machinic assemblage* of bodies. Keeping these two ideas in mind, we suggest that words are abstractions within communication, that is, that words are always more than simply representations of something. Words are shapes, configurations within the communication process that stress the assemblage of enunciation.

A posthuman/post-anthropocentric environmental communication theory becomes possible when thinking in terms of forces and affects is actualized. Posthuman environmental communication theory can be used as a method of analyzing ethical consequences in various projects and actions, and aims to reinvent the insistent urge in society to measure individuals against corporations and human survival against the usurpation of the planet, as, for example, in UNESCO’s “Man and Biosphere programme for sustainability.” This theory highlights the idea that human beings are incapable of reading forces or matters that are not those of bodies: “For man, as individual, is precisely defined as a figure of self-ownership, appropriation and survival, with the environment always being that which environs or surrounds a proper body” (Colebrook, “Calculus” 152). Posthuman environmental communication theory thus becomes a function of and a tool for understanding relational actions between social machines and desiring machines; as Colebrook notes, social machines are “the productive relation between bodies. Desiring machines are relations that are not yet organized according to named bodies” (“Legal” 18). Environmental communication in this way becomes political, and by being political, environmental communication enacts a posthuman ethical desire.

This ethical desire changes the anthropocentric philosophical discussion by modifying the questions “what am I?” and “why am I?” and instead opening up the capacity for infinite thought that is found in the question “what is love?” (MacCormack 148). The following words from MacCormack express the function of posthuman ethical thoughts quite well:

Posthuman Ethics asks not what the posthuman is, but how posthuman theory creates new, imaginative ways of understanding relations between lives. Ethics is a practice of activist, adaptive and creative interaction which avoids claims to overarching moral structures. *Posthuman Ethics* examines certain kinds of bodies to think new relations that offer liberty and a contemplation of the practices of power which have been exerted upon bodies. (1)

This ethical shift articulates an ethical desire within environmental communication for a posthuman turn that allows meaning within communicative actions to be understood as forces and affects within sensible relations, in and for life.

An environmental communication that works from within posthuman theory has the potential to problematize the often-taken-for-granted concepts ‘environment’ and ‘communication’. Such a challenge enables a turn from anthropocentrism to post-anthropocentrism, and opens up ethical desires that focus on posthuman needs. By affirming the relational communication that becomes in repetition and deterritorialization, in life and with life, these actions come to be understood as relationscapes for “new” or becoming territorializations.¹³

Environmental communication, from a posthuman perspective, is a function that challenges the present, when seen as a determined self-presence, by offering an open invitation for change when it comes to content and expression. It suggests a present that is a becoming future in process. Environmental communication thus works through the articulation of affirmative becoming, in which various nomadic posthuman subjects come to understand relationscapes by acknowledging posthuman relations.

What posthuman theory adds to environmental communication as a field of research and as a practice is the development of a post-anthropocentric perspective that considers environmental issues as relational; that is, it offers a process of desires within studied posthuman relationscapes from which to elaborate concepts such as sustainability. From the perspective of posthuman environmental communications, the concept ‘sustainability’ reflects the desires that can allow the earth to become a healthy and equalized spatiality *for* life and *about* life through various temporal relationscapes.

6. A Post-Anthropocentric Turn and the Desire for Sustainability

Here is an example of how a post-anthropocentric position might inform environmental communication. In the United Nations document *Our Common Future*, we see an environmental communication that aims “to achieve a just and healthy Earth” through activities that promote ‘sustainable development’. However, sustainable development as a concept consists of a word combination that might be read as contradictory, namely through the tension that emerges on the one hand from the constraints of the word ‘sustain’, which infers a conserving, protecting, and preserving of socio-physical relationships to guard them against change, and on the other hand from an understanding of the word ‘development’ as implying some sort of process incorporating progress that can cause positive change. In the UN document, sustainable development is described as follows:

Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It contains within it two key concepts:

- the concept of ‘needs’, in particular the essential needs of the world’s poor, to which overriding priority should be given; and

- the idea of limitations imposed by the state of technology and social organization on the environment's ability to meet present and future needs. (*Our Common Future*)

Here, sustainable development and sustainability are expressed in terms of a balancing of the world's resources, grounded in the management of nature's capacity to provide for the poor people of the world. This process comes to a start when a political body enters into relation with other bodies, such as, for example, in the so-called market (Colebrook, "Calculus" 151). Within communicative activities in which relational environmental actions matter, the concept 'sustainability' becomes an assemblage that participates in an economic machinery. In this sense, the concept 'development', as used in the United Nations document, treats nature in terms of an exclusively human environment that provides necessary resources for human beings. Nature's being seen as a resource for human beings to exploit indicates that it is being perceived through an anthropocentric worldview, in which ecological processes become economic issues for human society.

The human market system is an assemblage of human actors who define the activities that emerge through agents that are both nonhuman and human. Since economy is a matter of value, the economy becomes a method for evaluating ecological processes, and actions concerned with evaluating ecological processes involve environmental ethics, and are thus articulated as a moral effort. Issues involving environmental ethics are part of an ongoing discussion in which debates over where interest should be focused, along with notions of responsibility, are salient.¹⁴ Environmental ethics is of interest here, since the question of what needs there are and who the needy are involves ethical considerations within environmental communicative processes. MacCormack suggests the posthuman perspective in the following way: "a-human posthuman ethics offer[s] the possibility of threshold subjectivity" (119).¹⁵ The matter of being in need and the matter of needs themselves are not necessarily only concerns for humans, a fact that is pointed out by scholars such as Kalof and Fitzgerald; Peterson, Peterson, and Peterson; Wolfe; Kahn; and Monani. Within anthropocentric environmental communication, the formation of knowledge often only considers human needs and humans as being in need. This anthropocentric idea has been articulated as ecosystem services, or nature services, where nonhumans' actions are recognized as a valuable part of the economic market: "Ecosystem services are the conditions and processes through which natural ecosystems, and the species that make them up, sustain and fulfill human life" (Daily 3). 'Nature services', or 'Ecosystem services', frame nature and biodiversity within the human economic society that designates ecological processes as resources (Daily; Chapin, Kofinas, and Folke). In line with this, what is highly questionable is the apparatus by which ecological processes are represented as ecosystem services that articulate the actions of different agents as parts of a nonhuman assemblage, and thus as actors that are evaluated within the human labor market, which is equivalent to the human workforce. The apparatus is reduced to a function of machineries, which should not be confused with *the* machinery, that is, the becoming movement, the flow, and the actual actions in action (Deleuze and Guattari 559-560). Nonhuman actions, viewed as labor, will, in consequence, never give nonhuman agents anything but an instrumental position (Freeman), since labor is relational and has no value in itself (Peterson, Hall,

FeldPauscher-Parker, and Peterson 116, following Marx 588). To formulate ecosystem services is to formulate an articulation of ecological processes that recognizes and acknowledges the agents' actions as resources. Sometimes human actions are recognized as resources within society, and as such they are seen as resources without agency, and as a consequence some humans run the risk of being objectified (Taylor; Freeman). When people are turned into resources, it leads to a human-to-human interaction that, in turn, forms hierarchical divisions within and between human societies (Escobar, "Culture"; Escobar, "Ecology"; Jasanoff; Jahanbegloo and Shiva)

In "Culture Sits in Places" and "An Ecology of Difference," Arturo Escobar pays close attention to the forces inherent in human societies that affect their plurality, and also to the importance of critically acknowledging and recognizing this plurality. Feminist scholars such as Sheila Jasanoff, Vandana Shiva, Rosi Braidotti, and Donna Haraway raise critical arguments against the way evaluation of social machineries is affirmed and recognized in relation to the idea of a hierarchical and androcentric ecological order. Many scholars¹⁶ have acknowledged how nonhumans as well as dehumanized humans are relegated into a position of slavery, and recognized as slaves by the monetary markets. This recognition, moreover, provides an example of how relationality as an assemblage of forces and affects becomes a political, ecological, and economic matter that questions the androcentric forces within these social machines. But if environmental communication subscribes to "generating and debating multiple legitimate answers to the question of how to achieve a just and healthy Earth" (Peterson, Peterson, and Peterson 83), then "sustainability emerges ... as a central concept in social theory and it raises suitable complex questions of methodology" (Braidotti, *Transpositions* 206).

In line with these thoughts, sustainability becomes an anthropogenic matter for post- or non-anthropocentric articulations exploring human and nonhuman needs. Recognizing the needs of and behind the agents' actions is only a first step; these needs should also be acknowledged and affirmed as relational communicative actions for both human and nonhuman assemblages. When this is achieved, human and nonhuman agents involved in relational actions as partners become nomadic posthuman subjects that produce a real post-anthropocentric possibility.

Analogous with the terms 'ecosystem services' and 'nature services', we suggest the term 'biosphere services', which is the articulation of biosphere processes and relational actions that are formed and formulated within a post-human market. Furthermore, labor, seen as consisting of intra-actions, is a function necessary for creating possible machinic assemblages for post-human livelihood, which makes it possible to understand such assemblages as relationscapes. The concept 'biosphere services' thus explores post- or non-anthropocentric relational actions, in which biosphere services, as a concept, articulates activities in which human and nonhuman intra-actions and biosphere processes become processes for intra-change, by raising the value of life and the conditions for life. Biosphere processes, articulated through biosphere services, recognize the living and non-living material in these processes, which can then become acknowledged as having relational communicative value within forces affecting relationscapes.

Evaluation, as related to value, takes place when needs are articulated and conceptualized through recognition and acknowledgement of various human and non-human assemblages. A deterritorialized social assemblage involves participating allies in relationscapes. The intra-actions determine the exchange value for a post-anthropocentric market. Still, as long as the market refers to a human monetary economy, the possible gains for nonhumans can only be realized as an anthropogenic knowledge-formulating activity, because money has no value in a post-anthropocentric market.

Environmental communication concerning sustainable development as a concept and a practice is a process where sustainability materializes and articulates. Processes for sustainability involve actions in a liminal time-spatial situation where environmental communication expresses desires for “*a just and healthy Earth*” that are significant for a specific time-space situation or event.

7. Desires for a Just and Healthy Earth

A posthuman/post-anthropocentric ethics expresses a relational desire within a social machinery simultaneously with other desires, such as desires relating to survival, greed, and pleasure, and so connects specific bodies with a collective body to coordinate a shared spatiality through actions. We argue that various ethical desires are transformed within abstract machines to work through ideas relating to desirable repetitive actions that aim toward sustainability. Various repetitive actions express communicative forces that qualify certain possibilities or opportunities that in turn affect the communicative practice. From this perspective, repetitive actions become the organizing forces, generating organizations that transform desires into forces capable of communicating different ethical expressions.

If we argue that Environmental Philosophy formulates various ideas that matter within environmental ethics, this would be incompatible with the post-anthropocentric ideas by which the environment becomes a matter for post-human actions. Ethics, as Massumi writes, is about processuality, since ethics “is not about applying a critical judgment to expression’s product. It is about evaluating where its processual self-conversions lead” (xxvi). Ethics, as such a processual evaluation, produces, we suggest, a critical mapping from the reading of performative archives, which means that ethics becomes the tie that binds in relations both for and in a life that matters.

Situations that can be characterized as practices for and about sustainable development become through and within intra- and inter-actions, and this is what we would like to call the liminal actions in environmental communication. Inter-actions as well as intra-actions shape organizations¹⁷ through the repetitive actions of communicative practices, and the processuality of these communicative practices is the vehicle from which understanding and meaning materialize and are verbalized. In communicative acts, humans and nonhumans are continuously evaluated through various communicative practices that are intended for all forms of actions. This evaluation becomes an ethical issue that is important for pedagogical processes. That is, posthuman/post-

anthropocentric ethics is important because it verbalizes relational actions in relation to political matters that formalize desire, having an impact on all forms of pedagogical processes, such as education, teaching, or learning actions.

8. Concluding Remarks

In posthuman/post-anthropocentric terms, this text describes and develops the idea of a research perspective concerned with processuality, in which every situation is an event that matters. Posthuman environmental communication theory provides an answer to Rogers' desire to radically change the conceptions of humans, nature, material conditions, and discourse by enabling a "reconstruction of a different relationship to the environment in which we¹⁸ live" (268).

This perspective brings with it the recognition that a situation, an event, is an expression in which posthuman environmental communication theory provides an opportunity to understand the relational processes of life and in life. Moreover, the approach we have developed proposes a potential posthuman-postanthropocentric turn within environmental communication, which necessarily entails a consideration of a posthuman-postanthropocentric ethics.

Notes

¹ Constructivist ideas are used to formulate various models for managing both humans and nature, such as, e.g., social-ecological systems analysis and resilience theory (Chapin, Kofinas, and Folke; Schultz, Folke, and Olsson; Cox), or environmental communication analysis and environmental communication, as described by Jurin, Roush, and Danter. Post-structuralist, post-colonialist, and feminist theorists such as, e.g., Mellor; Peterson, Peterson, and Peterson; Chen, Milstein, Anguino, Sandoval, and Knudsen; Milstein (“Nature Identification”); and Rogers have challenged these ideas.

² As Peterson, Peterson, and Peterson write, for citizenship “to move beyond the division between speaking social subjects (humans), and silent objects (nonhumans), we must foreground the claim that humans and extrahumans interact by modifying each other’s experiences and consequences.... [S]ince extrahumans are real, in that they experience and are social, their citizenship and subjecthood hinges on their ability to participate in political discourse.... Extrahumans, however, cannot gain citizenship in political communities without spokespersons in the political process of decision-making” (78).

³ “Assemblage” denotes that things do not have a single, stable identity or essence; rather, “they affirm a view in which disparate ‘sub-elements’ of the world are combined/combinable in many different ways to constitute what we think of as things and processes: bodily organs and persons, valleys and nations. What exists is the more or less random and temporary collection or assemblage of affects and events, now combined one way, then another” (Mugerauer 188).

⁴ Differentiation opens “thinking to powers of difference beyond the concept” (Colebrook, *Deleuze* 10). “In a bifurcating world, a multiplicity is defined not by its center but by the limits and borders where it enters into relations with other multiplicities and changes nature, transforms itself” (Smith 203).

⁵ Repetition refers to the idea of ‘becoming body’, not as representational, but actually and materially; “each repetition and re-articulation is open to new determinations and senses” (Colebrook, *Deleuze* 80). “[T]rue repetition addresses something singular, unchangeable, and different, without ‘identity’. Instead of exchanging the similar and identifying the Same, it authenticates the different” (Deleuze, *Logic* 287).

⁶ Börebäck writes about the procedures of environmental communication in two biosphere reserves that express organizations through the notions of agonistic pluralism in one place and deliberative consensus in another.

⁷ Considering the whole universe, this is an idea that is relational rather than subject-centered. The notion of the universe is today post-heliocentric with various competing ideas regarding explanations, often connected to the Big Bang theory and Einstein’s relativity theory.

⁸ As Colman states, “Affect is the *intensive power* that propels extensive actions” (84). “The affection-image registers a process of interval that occurs in between perception and action; the juncture where something happens. This place, this domain, this juncture, this encounter, are all sites where the affection-image creates a change — this may be chemical, sensorial, structural, durational, intellectual, cognitive, perceptual — a relational affect” (Colman 84-85).

⁹ ‘Striated space’, write Deleuze and Guattari, “is defined by the requirements of long-distance vision: constancy of orientation, invariance of distance through an interchange of inertial points of reference, interlinkage by immersion in an ambient milieu, constitution of central perspective” (545).

¹⁰ Deleuze and Guattari define ‘line of flight’ [*ligne de fuite*] in the following way: “Multiplicities are defined by the outside: by the abstract line, the line of flight or deterritorialization according to which they change in nature and connect with other multiplicities. The plane of consistency (grid) is the outside of all multiplicities. The line of flight marks: the reality of a finite number of dimensions that the multiplicity effectively fills; the impossibility of a supplementary dimension, unless the multiplicity is transformed by the line of flight; the possibility and necessity of flattening all of the multiplicities on a single plane of consistency or exteriority, regardless of their number of dimensions” (9-10).

¹¹ As Parisi states, Barad “draws from Bohr’s distinction between the interaction of independent entities (or *relata*) and intra-action of *relata*-within-phenomena. For Bohr, *relata* are not prior to intra-active components. Rather, specific intra-actions make *relata* dependent on phenomena” (Parisi 78).

¹² As Barad says, the “causal relationship between the apparatuses of bodily production and the phenomena produced is one of agential intra-action” (*Meeting* 139).

¹³ On ‘territorialization’ Deleuze and Guattari note the following: “[A] territorialized, assembled function acquires enough independence to constitute a new assemblage, one that is more or less deterritorialized, *en route* to deterritorialization” (Deleuze and Guattari 357). And they also states, “[T]he territorial assemblage territorializes functions and forces (sexuality, aggressiveness, gregariousness, etc.), and in the process of territorializing them, transforms them. But these territorialized functions and forces can suddenly take on an autonomy that makes them swing over into other assemblages, compose other deterritorialized assemblages” (Deleuze and Guattari 358-359).

¹⁴ There are numerous scholars who write on environmental ethical thinking, such as Aldo Leopold, whose *Sand County Almanac* explores ideas regarding management as a relational action of thinking with nature. Similarly, Arne Næss argues for an ecosophy recognizing the inherent value of all living beings (Næss and Sessions). This particular form of ecosophy, called deep ecology, aims to shape environmental policies from

ecosophical tenets (Næss and Sessions). Mark Rowland developed a critical alternative to the idea of inherent value, and criticized, for example, evolution with his notion of affordances. Rosi Braidotti (*Posthuman*), Jane Bennett, and Patricia MacCormack have all developed the idea of a posthuman ethics and its consequences.

¹⁵ “Threshold(s) are the becoming that refuse the fathomless empty space between meaning and communication, living as legal status, subject communicating transcendently to like subject, the space often filled by the bodies of women, animals, the queer, diffabled, the monstrous, for symbolic and actual exchange between subjects and their relationship with knowledge and consumption” (MacCormack 121).

¹⁶ Among these scholars can be mentioned, for example, Haraway, Benhabib, Jahanbegloo and Shiva, and Peterson, Peterson, and Peterson.

¹⁷ This follows how Spoelstra (84) and Massumi express organization, of which Börebäck gives an example, showing how inter- and intra-actions are significant for organizing environmental communication and the meaning-making process.

¹⁸ By “we” Rogers refers to humans, but the authors of this essay suggest that “we” involves both human and nonhumans.

References

- Barad, Karen. *Meeting the Universe Halfway: Quantum Physics and the Entanglement of Matter and Meaning*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2007.
- . "Posthumanist Performativity: Toward an Understanding of How Matter Comes to Matter." *Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society* 28.3 (Spring 2003): 801-831.
- Benhabib, Seyla. *Autonomi och Gemenskap: Kommunikativ etik feminism och postmodernism*. Trans. Annika Persson. Göteborg: Daidalos, 1992.
- Bennett, Jane. *Vibrant Matter: A Political Ecology of Things*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2010.
- Börebäck, Maria Kristina. "UNESCO Man and Biosphere Reserves: The Significance of Communication Processes in the Formation of Model-Areas for Sustainability-Two Case Study." *International Journal of Environmental Sustainability* 8.4 (2013); 55-69.
- Braidotti, Rosi. "Locating Deleuze's Eco-Philosophy between Bio/Zoe-Power and Necro-Politics." In Rosi Braidotti, Claire Colebrook, and Patrick Hanafin, eds. *Deleuze and Law: Forensic Futures*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009. 96-116.
- . *The Posthuman*. Cambridge: Polity Press, 2013.
- . *Transpositions*. Cambridge: Polity Press, 2010.
- Chapin, F. Stuart, III, Gary P. Kofinas, and Carl Folke, eds. *Principles of Ecosystem Stewardship: Resilience-Based Natural Resource Management in a Changing World*. New York: Springer, 2009.
- Chen, Yea-Wen, Tema Milstein, Claudia Anguiano, Jennifer Sandoval, and Lissa Knudsen. "Challenges and Benefits of Community-Based Participatory Research for Environmental Justice: A Case of Collaboratively Examining Ecocultural Struggles." *Environmental Communication* 6.3 (September 2012): 403-421.
- Colebrook, Claire. "The Calculus of Individual Worth." In Tom Cohen, Claire Colebrook, J. Hillis Miller, and Paul de Man. *Theory and the Disappearing Future: On de Man, On Benjamin*. London: Routledge, 2012. 130-162.
- . *Deleuze and the Meaning of Life*. London: Continuum, 2010.

JPSE: Journal for the Philosophical Study of Education III (2018)

- . "From Radical Representations to Corporeal Becomings: The Feminist Philosophy of Lloyd, Grosz, and Gatens." *Hypatia* 15.2 (2000): 76-93.
- . "Legal Theory after Deleuze." In Rosi Graidotti, Claire Colebrook, and Patrick Hanafin, eds. *Deleuze and Law: Forensic Futures*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009. 6-23.
- . "Stratigraphic Time, Women's Time." *Australian Feminist Studies* 24.59 (March 2009): 11-16.
- Colman, Felicity. *Deleuze and Cinema: The Film Concepts*. Oxford: Berg Bloomsbury Publishing, 2011.
- Cox, Robert. "Nature's 'Crisis Disciplines': Does Environmental Communication Have an Ethical Duty?" *Environmental Communication* 1.1 (2007): 5-20.
- Daily, Gretchen C. "Introduction: What Are Ecosystem Services?" In Gretchen Daily, ed. *Nature's Services: Societal Dependence on Natural Ecosystems*. Washington, DC: Island Press, 1997. 3-10.
- Deleuze, Gilles. *Foucault*. Trans. and ed. Seán Hand. London: Continuum, 1999.
- . *The Logic of Sense*. Ed. Constantin V. Boundas. Trans. Mark Lester and Charles Stivale. London: Athlone Press, 1990.
- . *Pure Immanence: Essays on a Life*. Trans. Anne Boyman. New York: Zone Books, 2001.
- Deleuze, Gilles, and Félix Guattari. *A Thousand Plateaus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*. Trans. Brian Massumi. London: Continuum, 2008.
- Deleuze, Gilles, and Claire Parnet. *Dialogues*. Trans. Hugh Tomlinson and Barbara Habberjam. New York: Columbia University Press, 1977.
- Dryzek, John S. *Deliberative Democracy and Beyond: Liberals, Critics, Contestations*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2002.
- Escobar, Arturo. "Culture Sits in Places: Reflections on Globalism and Subaltern Strategies of Localization." *Political Geography* 20 (2001): 139-174.
- . "An Ecology of Difference: Equality and Conflict in a Glocalised World." *Focaal: European Journal of Anthropology* 47 (2006): 120-137.
- Freeman, R. Edward. *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010.

JPSE (2018)

Haraway, Donna J. "Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the Privilege of Partial Perspective." *Feminist Studies* 14.3 (Autumn 1988): 575-599.

---. *When Species Meet*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2008.

Harding, Sandra. *The Science Question in Feminism*. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 1986.

Harper, Douglas. *Communication*. Online Etymology Dictionary, 2001-2017, www.etymonline.com/index.php?allowed_in_frame=0&search=communication. Accessed 30 December 2017.

---. *Environment*. Online Etymology Dictionary, 2001-2017, www.etymonline.com/index.php?term=environment. Accessed 30 December 2017.

Hayles, N. Katherine. *How We Became Posthuman: Virtual Bodies in Cybernetics, Literature, and Informatics*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1999.

Jahanbegloo, Ramin, and Vandana Shiva. *Talking Environment: Vandana Shiva in Conversation with Ramin Jahanbegloo*. New Dehli: Oxford University Press, 2013.

Jasanoff, Sheila. "Ordering Knowledge, Ordering Society." In Sheila Jasanoff, ed. *States of Knowledge. The Co-production of Science and Social Order*, London: Routledge, 2004. 13-45.

Jenlink, Patrick M., and Bela H. Banathy. "Preface." *Dialogue as a Collective Means of Design Conversation*. Ed. Patrick M. Jenlink and Bela H. Banathy. Carmel, CA: Springer, 2008. xi-xii.

Jurin, Richard R., Donny Roush, and K. Jeffrey Danter. *Environmental Communication: Skills and Principles for Natural Resource Managers, Scientists, and Engineers*. 2nd ed. Dordrecht: Springer, 2010.

Kahn, Richard V. *Critical Pedagogy, Ecopedagogy & Planetary Crisis: The Ecopedagogy Movement*. New York: Peter Lang Publishing Inc., 2010.

Kalof, Linda, and Amy Fitzgerald. *The Animals Reader: The Essential Classic and Contemporary Writings*. Oxford: Berg Publisher, 2007.

Kennedy, Barbara. "... of butterflies, bodies and biograms ... Affective Spaces in Performativities in the Performance of *Madama Butterfly*." In Laura Cull, ed. *Deleuze and Performance*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2009. 183-202.

JPSE: Journal for the Philosophical Study of Education III (2018)

- Leopold, Aldo. *A Sand County Almanac, With Essays on Conservation from Round River*. New York: Ballantine Books, 1970.
- Littlejohn, Stephen W., and Karen. A. Foss, eds. *Encyclopedia of Communication Theory*, vol. 1. Los Angeles: SAGE Publication Inc., 2009.
- MacCormack, Patricia. *Posthuman Ethics: Embodiment and Social Theory*. Farnham, UK: Ashgate Publishing Limited, 2012.
- Manning, Erin. *Relationescapes: Movement, Art, Philosophy*. Technologies of Lived Abstraction Series. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 2009.
- Marx, Karl. *Capital: A Critique of Political Economy, Volume I: The Process of Capitalist Production*. Trans. Samuel Moore and Edward Aveling. Chicago: Charles H. Kerr, 1909.
- Massumi, Brian. *A Shock to Thought: Expression After Deleuze and Guattari*. London: Routledge Taylor and Francis, 2002.
- Mellor, Mary. *Feminism and Ecology*. Cambridge: Polity Press, 1997.
- Milstein, Tema. "Environmental Communication." In Littlejohn and Foss, eds. 344-349.
- . "Nature Identification: The Power of Pointing and Naming." *Environmental Communication* 5.1 (2011): 3-24.
- Monani, Salma. "At the Intersection of Ecosee and Just Sustainability: New Directions for Communication Theory and Practice." *Environmental Communication* 5.2 (2011): 141-145.
- Mugerauer, Robert. "Deleuze and Guattari's Return to Science as a Basis for Environmental Philosophy." In Bruce V. Foltz and Robert Frodeman, eds. *Rethinking Nature: Essays in Environmental Philosophy*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2004, 180-204.
- Næss, Arne, and George Sessions. "The Deep Ecology Platform." In Nina Witoszek and Andrew Brennan, eds. *Philosophical Dialogues: Arne Næss and the Progress of Ecophilosophy*. Lanham, MD: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers Inc., 1999. 8-9.
- Parisi, Luciana. "The Adventures of a Sex." In Chrysanthi Nigianni and Merl Storr, eds. *Deleuze and Queer Theory*. Deleuze Connections. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2009. 72-91.
- Peters, John Durham. *Speaking into the Air: A History of the Idea of Communication*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1999.

JPSE (2018)

- Peterson, Markus J., Damon M. Hall, Andreas M. FeldPauscher-Parker, and Tarla Rai Peterson. "Obscuring Ecosystem Function with Application of the Ecosystem Services Concept." *Conservation Biology* 24.1 (February 2010): 113-119.
- Peterson, M. Nils, Markus J. Peterson, and Tarla Rai Peterson. "Response to Cox, 'Environmental Communication: Why This Crisis Discipline Should Facilitate Environmental Democracy'." *Environmental Communication* 1.1 (May 2007): 74-86.
- Rogers, Richard A. "Overcoming the Objectification of Nature in Constitutive Theories: Toward a Transhuman, Materialist Theory of Communication." *Western Journal of Communication* 62.3 (Summer 1998): 244-272.
- Rowlands, Mark. *The Environmental Crisis: Understanding the Value of Nature*. Houndmills, UK: Palgrave Macmillan, 2000.
- Ryther, Catherine. "Who Emerges in Conversation? An Abolitionist Interruption that Teaches." *Reconstruction: Studies in Contemporary Culture* 14.2 (2014): x1-x22, reconstruction.eserver.org/Issues/142/contents_142.shtml.
- Schultz, Lisen, Carl Folke, and Per Olsson. "Enhancing Ecosystem Management Through Social-Ecological Inventories: Lessons from Kristianstads Vattenrike, Sweden." *Environmental Conservation* 34.2 (June 2007): 140-152.
- Smith, Daniel W. "'Life.'" In *Essays on Deleuze* by Daniel W. Smith. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2012. 189-221.
- Spoelstra, Sverre. *What is Organization?* Lund Studies in Economics and Management 96. Lund, Sweden: Lund Business Press, 2007.
- Sriskandarajah, Nadarajah, and Arjen E. J. Wals. "Mediated Cross-Cultural Learning in the Pursuit of Sustainability." *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension* 16.1 (March 2010): 1-3.
- Taylor, Frederick Winslow. *The Principles of Scientific Management*. New York: Courier Dover Publications/Harper Brothers, 1998.
- United Nations, World Commission on Environment and Development. *United Nations. Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our Common Future*. Transmitted to the General Assembly as Annex to document A/42/427, 1987, www.un-documents.net/wced-ofc.htm. Accessed 2 January 2018.
- Wals, Aarjen E. J. "Between Knowing What Is Right and Knowing That Is It Wrong to Tell Others What Is Right: On Relativism, Uncertainty and Democracy in

JPSE: Journal for the Philosophical Study of Education III (2018)

- Environmental and Sustainability Education.” *Environmental Education Research* 16.1 (2010): 143-151.
- Wolfe, Dylan. “The Video Rhizome: Taking Technology Seriously in *The Matrix*.” *Environmental Communication: A Journal of Nature and Culture* 3.3 (November 2009): 317-334.